

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Some Aldoses by Chromium Peroxydichromate in very Dilute Sulphuric Acid^(a)

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The oxidation of D-galactose, D-xylose and L-arabinose by chromium peroxydichromate has been studied in very dilute sulphuric acid (0.12-0.066 N). The reaction is of first order each in substrate, oxidant and sulphuric acid. HCrO_4^- ion appears to be the predominant oxidant. Neutral salts and Mn(II) have retarding effect on the reaction. A mechanism which is consistent with the observed rate laws and experimental facts has been proposed.

OXIDATION of D-glucose by chromium peroxydichromate was studied by Sharma *et al.*¹. The present paper deals with the kinetic studies on the oxidation of some more aldoses like D-galactose, D-xylose and L-arabinose. The results have been used to evaluate the general features of oxidation in dilute sulphuric acid and steps involved in it.

Experimental

Chromium peroxydichromate was prepared by the method of Singh and Rai². Fresh solutions of D-galactose (Loba-Chemie), D-xylose (Hopkins and William) and L-arabinose (B.D.H.) were employed. Other chemicals used in the study were of B.D.H., AnalaR grade. The course of the reaction was followed by estimating unreacted chromium(VI) iodometrically.

Results and Discussion

All aldoses under study showed aldonic acids³ as oxidation products. The reaction thus can be represented stoichiometrically as :

The kinetics of the oxidation of aldoses with peroxydichromate was investigated at several initial concentration of the reactants. The pseudo first order rate constants (k_1) were calculated from the integrated form of the first order rate equation (Table 1). Plot of $\log(a-x)$ vs time shows the nature of first order dependence in oxidant (Fig. 1).

Values of $k_2 = \frac{k_1}{[\text{aldose}]}$ are consistent indicating that the order with substrates is unity (Table 2).

TABLE 1—DEPENDENCE ON PEROXYDICHROMATE CONCENTRATION

[Peroxydichromate] $\times 10^3 \text{ N}$	$10^3 k_1, \text{ min}^{-1}$		
	Galactose	Xylose	Arabinose
1.00	3.80	2.34	3.72
1.25	3.78	2.18	3.55
1.66	3.72	2.15	3.31
2.50	3.64	2.12	2.93
5.00	—	2.08	2.56

Acid dependence : The rate study measurements at several initial concentration of sulphuric acid exhibited a uniform increase in pseudo first order constant with increasing $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ (Table 3). The slope of the plot $\log k_1$ vs $\log [\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ for all the aldoses under study shows unity, indicating that the reaction is first order dependent in acid (Fig. 2).

Salts like Na_2SO_4 , K_2SO_4 and MnSO_4 are found to have retarding effect on the reaction rate. The rate was also found to increase with decrease in dielectric constant of the medium which was varied by using acetic acid-water mixture. Plot of $\log k_1$ vs $1/D$ shows a linear relationship. This clearly indicates the involvement of positively charged species which are active in the rate determining step.

The reactions were studied at four different temperatures. Plot of $\log k_1$ vs $1/T$ confirms Arrhenius relationship. The values of activation parameters are recorded in Table 4.

(a) (i) Xylose studies were presented at the Annual Convention of Chemists, 1980.

(ii) Arabinose studies were presented in the Symposium on 'Kinetics and mechanism of chemical reactions', University of Allahabad, 1980.

TABLE 2—DEPENDENCE ON ALDOSE CONCENTRATION

A— $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7)_3 = 1.66 \times 10^{-3} \text{ N}$; $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 2.50 \times 10^{-2} \text{ N}$; Temp. 50°
 B— $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7)_3 = 2.50 \times 10^{-3} \text{ N}$; $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 2.50 \times 10^{-2} \text{ N}$; Temp. 50°
 C— $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7)_3 = 2.50 \times 10^{-3} \text{ N}$; $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 2.50 \times 10^{-2} \text{ N}$; Temp. 50°

[Aldose] M	A		B		C	
	$10^3 k_1$ min ⁻¹	$\frac{10^4 k_1}{[\text{Galactose}]}$ 1 mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	$10^3 k_1$ min ⁻¹	$\frac{10^4 k_1}{[\text{Xylose}]}$ 1 mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	$10^3 k_1$ min ⁻¹	$\frac{10^4 k_1}{[\text{Arabinose}]}$ 1 mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
0.10	0.76	7.60	0.40	4.00	0.89	8.90
0.20	1.53	7.65	—	—	1.84	9.20
0.25	2.03	8.12	—	—	—	—
0.30	2.51	8.36	1.23	4.10	2.95	9.83
0.35	3.03	8.65	—	—	—	—
0.40	3.72	9.30	1.65	4.12	4.19	10.47
0.50	4.91	9.82	2.12	4.25	5.42	10.84
0.75	7.23	9.64	3.48	4.64	7.63	10.17
1.00	9.86	9.86	4.50	4.50	10.38	10.38
	Av. $\frac{10^4 k_1}{[\text{D-galactose}]}$ = 8.74 ± 0.85		Av. $\frac{10^4 k_1}{[\text{D-xylose}]}$ = 4.26 ± 0.22		Av. $\frac{10^4 k_1}{[\text{D-arabinose}]}$ = 9.97 ± 0.51	

Mechanism: In aqueous solution chromium peroxydichromate decomposes as⁴⁻⁶:

The peroxy oxygen reacts with aldose to give aldonic acid.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

TABLE 3—DEPENDENCE ON ACID CONCENTRATION

$[\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7)_3] = 1.66 \times 10^{-3} \text{ N}$; $[\text{Galactose}] = 4.00 \times 10^{-1} \text{ M}$; Temp. 50°
 $[\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7)_3] = 2.50 \times 10^{-3} \text{ N}$; $[\text{Xylose}] = 5.00 \times 10^{-1} \text{ M}$; Temp. 50°
 $[\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7)_3] = 2.50 \times 10^{-3} \text{ N}$; $[\text{Arabinose}] = 3.00 \times 10^{-1} \text{ M}$; Temp. 50°

$[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ 10^3 N	$10^3 k_1 \text{ min}^{-1}$		
	Galactose	Xylose	Arabinose
1.25	—	1.13	1.40
1.66	—	1.33	—
2.00	3.05	—	—
2.50	3.72	2.12	2.93
3.33	5.04	—	3.81
5.00	8.08	4.91	5.75
6.66	10.04	—	—

TABLE 4—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS

Aldose	E k cal. mole ⁻¹	A sec ⁻¹	ΔS e.u.
D-Galactose	13.57	9.39 × 10 ⁶	-31.37
D-Xylose	15.40	10.9 × 10 ⁶	-31.07
D-Arabinose	11.98	6.10 × 10 ⁶	-29.00

Since rate of oxidation decreases with increase in oxidant concentration, it is obvious that the active species in the oxidation is HCrO_4^- of Cr(VI) ,⁷

and oxidises aldoses to their aldonic acid in presence of H^+ . The steps involved are :

Applying steady state treatment to the intermediate, it can be shown that the rate of reaction depends on the unit concentration of aldose, H^+ and oxidant.

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